

DESCRIPTION OF URBAN AGGLOMERATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction . Today, as a result of the use of geocity constructions, large-scale works are being carried out in order to improve the socio-economic lifestyle of the population in our republic. In particular, relations between the city and the organization of the scientific development of urban systems are gaining importance. This type of research is also considered relevant from the point of view of organization and production , and issues related to maintaining industrial efficiency through the complex organization of the national economy, which have a strong impact on the socio-demographic situation in the agglomeration zone, are considered. The problems of organizing a comfortable lifestyle of the population , the issues of creating an innovative and investment environment, and the indicators of urbanization of the regions of our country are being analyzed.

Main . Territorial placement of production forces in the Republic of Uzbekistan and stable socio-economic development at the current stage, structural changes in the territorial organization of industrial sectors are growing, this is a process specific to the conditions of market relations. It is reflected in the stratification of urbanization in the regions in the settlement of settlements. If we take a broader approach, the problems of territorial settlement of the population of economic regions are the main direction of demographic processes in the republic. Solving urban problems of a macro-economic nature on a regional scale, studying demographic factors and growth trends in modern settlements, forming real urban agglomeration systems and their implementation includes evaluation of functions. In the studies of experts, it was found that the ways of development of agglomerations are different. However, although the development of agglomeration is different, there are two main development from "city" and "region". In the first case, a monocentric, that is, a single center is formed, and in the second, a polycentric multi-centered agglomeration is formed. It should be noted that the most large cities are naturally and naturally becoming monocentric agglomerations. They attract

modern science , culture, management and great people around them . Thus, the system of cities and villages around the agglomerations is formed as a result of the superposition of two opposing currents controlled by the largest center. In the first, everything tends to settle down from the city - the center, but the possibilities of the city have already been exhausted and now only satellite cities can grow. Pendulum migration, which connects all of these within the framework of neighboring, close and sometimes mutual influence, is also characteristic of monocentric agglomerations. That is, every day people come to the center to work from the city, neighboring cities and towns, as well as from rural areas. This stream reached more than one hundred thousand inhabitants in the Tashkent agglomeration. The flow of population is moving towards the city center from satellite cities . The formation of agglomerations developing from the "region" happens differently. For example, in the conditions of increasing natural needs with high concentration of raw material reserves, the resources of such centers will increase more and more. In the last twenty years, during the years of Uzbekistan's independence, many scientists and researchers have dealt with the problems of cities and urban agglomeration. Among them, it was studied by ZMAkramov, TIRaimov, EAAhmedov, OBOta-Mirzayev, AAQayumov, RXMurtazaev, VLGenshtek, ASSoliyev, Sh.A.Azimov and others. Researchers compare the Tashkent agglomeration with other regions of the republic. Tashkent economic region includes Tashkent agglomeration and adjacent districts. It is the leading region of the country in the development of infrastructure sectors, equal to the volume of the gross domestic product (24.9% of the total volume of the country). Compared to other regions of our republic, there are more qualified personnel capable of producing innovative products. Five large urban agglomerations were formed in the region: 1) Northeast;

- 2) North ;
- 3) South ;
- 4) South -west
- 5) North -west

Population growth is mainly due to natural and partly mechanical movement, as well as the percentage of pendulum migration is increasing. Despite the fact that the agglomeration continues to produce new specialists with high innovation skills, it is experiencing a shortage of workers. The core and surroundings of Tashkent agglomeration perform different functions. In the central core of the multifunctional city, memorial monuments are located, the role of such functions as history, culture, and tourism is increasing, and there are also all

administrative, economic, cultural and educational functions of the settlement system. For this reason, the relocation of the population to new areas reduces the role of industry, and green belts are created. The Tashkent agglomeration is divided into two large zones: the first covers areas such as Keles, Eshonguzar, Nazarbek, Koksaroy, Yangibozor, Salor, which are located near the city of Tashkent. The population density is more than 600-700 people per km. The second zone of the Tashkent agglomeration stretches for 60-70 km, with a density of 200-250 people. So, in the second zone, satellite cities of Tashkent are located and they form suburbs. Viticulture, vegetable, dairy, and heavy industries have been formed in these regions.

Fergana Valley is a populated and developed region since ancient times. Namangan, Andijan and Fergana are located along transport routes and major main irrigation systems. With the introduction of large-scale irrigation agriculture, settlements in the Fergana Valley have changed rapidly and this situation continues to this day. More than 40% of the population of the region are rural residents, and an agro-industrial complex has formed in the region. The vegetable and dairy industries of the cities are well developed. The balance of migration as a result of trips in the region is positive. Intensification of production in Ferghana, rapid development of the infrastructure networks of the valley and its regions, solving problems of labor resources are the most important factors of the development of the region.

Southern economic regions are the least urbanized region of our country and located in the southernmost part of the country. In this region, the agricultural sector is dominant, and thin fiber cotton and fruit are grown on irrigated lands. But for the development of agriculture, the dry climate has a negative effect. Therefore, water reservoirs and irrigation facilities were built to develop irrigated lands. During the years of independence, transport and economic relations were developed in the region. There are two sectors in the south: manufacturing industrial complexes, i.e. fuel-energy industry and agro-industrial complex. With the development of industry, the number of cities and the percentage of the population is increasing year by year.

The following factors affect the high economic potential and specialization of the Zarafshan economic region.

- Highly qualified labor resources;
- Historically formed production branches;
- Availability of natural resources;
- Geographical location of the region;

- Agroclimatic;
- Soil resources;
- Availability of energy resources;

Energy-intensive sectors and technical crops, vegetables, rice, potatoes and cereals are grown in the region. The central location of the economic district serves as a link for the Tashkent agglomeration and the lower regions of the Fergana Valley.

Lower Amudarya economic region covers the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Thus, in the years of independence, soda production began. Production of gas condensate began on the basis of the mine. 11.2% of the population of our republic lives there. The share of urban population in the district is high, especially in Nukus agglomeration. Nevertheless, the agglomerations in the Republic of Karakalpakstan are still not well formed .. The developing agglomerations are Khojayli , Tortkol, Beruniy, Kunghirot, Chimboy and others. In Lower Amudarya, 70% of the working- age population is employed in material production sectors, which is much higher than the national average.

Summary. When the population of the city reaches 100,000 people , it starts to become an urban agglomeration. GMLappo generally defines cities with at least 250 inhabitants as forming large polycentric urban agglomerations. By the end of the 20th century, there were about 1,500 agglomerations in the world, each of which had more than 100,000 inhabitants. Almost 10 years later, the number of agglomerations and their population has increased significantly. Thus, agglomerations are closely related urban and urban systems. The development of problems in the urban agglomeration is a management lever that actively affects the stabilization of the situation in the republic.

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